

The new Open Finance paradigm in light of the FIDA Regulation and PSD3 proposals

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Introduction

The European Commission's recent proposals of Financial Data Access Regulation (FIDA) and new Payment Service Directive (PSD3) represent a turning point in the regulation of the most data-driven digital finance applications in the internal market. In particular, PSD3 aims at modernizing the already innovative PSD2 discipline on payment services and open banking in order to promote enhanced security, efficiency and accessibility; instead FIDA is primarily aimed at promoting competition and innovation in the field of financial services and open finance, namely through a more secure and broader processing of users' financial data, amending to this end several existing EU regulations in the financial sector and non-financial sectors, including the recent EU Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA).

Methods

The method of analysis will be that of legal studies in the field of economic law, thus following an approach not limited to a positivist approach to law, but also considering the dynamic dimension of the relations and interactions with the economic and financial phenomenon being regulated.

Results

The analysis is intended to analyze the scope of the proposed regulatory innovations and their consistency with other relevant legal principles regulatory frameworks, highlighting the relating benefits for consumers, competitiveness, inclusiveness and security of the Union's financial system. The possible regulatory obstacles to the implementation of the PSD3 and FIDA proposals and the most sensitive aspects for their implementation in the Italian legal system will also be assessed.

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